

COMPARATIVE FATIGUE LIFE ASSESSMENT OF HYBRID ALUMINUM-GFRP AND TI6AL4V-GFRP CYLINDERS SUBJECTED TO CYCLIC LOADING: A NUMERICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites are extensively employed in lightweight structural applications due to their high specific strength and stiffness. To further enhance the structural performance of thin composite shells, metallic stiffeners such as ring and helical configurations are commonly integrated. In this study, a numerical investigation is carried out to evaluate the fatigue performance of hybrid GFRP shell–aluminium stiffened cylindrical structures subjected to cyclic loading. The developed finite element model examines the influence of aluminium helical and ring stiffeners on structural stiffness and fatigue life of the composite cylindrical shell under lateral and longitudinal loading conditions. Cyclic loading is applied to capture stiffness degradation and damage evolution in the hybrid system, allowing for a comparative assessment of stiffener configurations. This study provides the effectiveness of aluminium ring stiffeners provide stiffness retention, structural integrity, and improved fatigue performance under both loading directions. This study also highlight the critical role of stiffener geometry in governing fatigue behaviour and damage progression in hybrid aluminium–GFRP cylindrical shells. The present study provides valuable insights for the design of durable, lightweight, and fatigue-resistant composite structures for advanced engineering applications.

Keywords – Fatigue strength, Helical stiffeners, cyclic loading, lightweight hybrid design, Transient structural analysis, Eigen buckling analysis,

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite structures are engineered materials formed by combining two or more distinct constituents to achieve enhanced properties such as a high strength-to-weight ratio, design flexibility, corrosion resistance, and improved fatigue and impact performance, along with favourable thermal and electrical insulation characteristics. Owing to these advantages, composite structures are widely used in industries including aerospace, automotive, construction, and sports equipment, where lightweight, durable, and high-performance materials are required. Among various composite systems, fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are the most commonly employed for developing strong and stiff structural components. In FRP composites, high-strength fibres are embedded within a polymer matrix, where the fibres act as the primary load-carrying elements, while the matrix ensures effective load transfer, structural integrity, and environmental protection. FRP components can be manufactured using a range of conventional processing techniques, enabling flexibility in geometry and structural design for complex engineering applications. In recent years, several experimental studies have been carried out to investigate the mechanical behaviour, stiffness characteristics, and failure mechanisms of fibre-reinforced composite structures under different loading conditions. However, comparatively fewer numerical investigations have been reported, despite their importance in predicting the structural response and damage behaviour of complex composite components. The objective of the present study is to numerically investigate the influence of ring and helical stiffeners on the structural behaviour of FRP composite cylindrical shells subjected to axial and lateral compression. The study focuses on two stiffener configurations—ring and helical—and examines their effects on stiffness and overall mechanical response under different loading scenarios. Two loading conditions are considered: compression between two rigid flat platens and compression between one rigid flat platen and a cylindrical indenter. The outcomes of this research are expected to provide improved insight into the role of stiffener configuration in enhancing the structural performance of FRP composite cylindrical shells and to support the design of efficient and reliable composite structures.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Composite materials, particularly fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites, have gained widespread attention in aerospace, marine, automotive, and energy applications due to their high specific strength, stiffness, and corrosion resistance. The mechanical behaviour of composite structures is strongly influenced by fibre architecture, stacking sequence, winding angle, and the presence of defects or stiffeners. As a result, extensive experimental, analytical, and numerical studies have been conducted over the past two decades to understand the strength, damage, energy absorption, and fatigue behaviour of composite cylindrical structures.

The fundamental theories governing the mechanics and failure behaviour of composite materials were comprehensively presented by Kaw (2006), providing the analytical foundation for laminate theory, failure criteria, and composite structural modelling [1]. Building on these fundamentals, Meijer and Ellyin (2008) experimentally established a failure envelope for $\pm 60^\circ$ filament-wound glass fibre reinforced epoxy tubes [2]. Their work demonstrated that maximum strain criteria can effectively predict failure strains in filament-wound tubular structures, offering a baseline for subsequent experimental and numerical investigations.

Early studies focused on impact resistance and lateral loading behaviour of filament-wound composite tubes. Hafeez and Almaskari (2015) investigated the scaling laws governing damage growth in laterally indented filament-wound tubes and showed that damage evolution follows consistent trends when scaled using non-dimensional parameters [3]. Similarly, Chiu et al. (2015) examined the crushing response of composite cylinders under quasi-static and dynamic loading conditions and reported that energy absorption was largely strain-rate independent due to fibre-dominated fracture mechanisms [4]. These studies highlighted the inherent energy absorbing capability of composite cylindrical shells.

The role of structural enhancement through stiffening was addressed by Moeinifard et al. (2016), who conducted experimental investigations on unstiffened and grid-stiffened composite cylindrical shells under lateral compression [5]. Their results revealed that grid stiffeners significantly increased structural stiffness, contact force, and energy absorption, particularly during the elastic deformation stage. This finding underlined the importance of stiffener configuration in improving structural performance. In a related study, Gemi et al. (2018) examined concrete confinement using $\pm 55^\circ$ filament-wound glass/epoxy pipes and demonstrated substantial improvements in compressive strength and ductility, while identifying multiple failure mechanisms such as delamination and fibre splitting [6].

Several studies have focused on damage initiation and progression in filament-wound composite structures. Chaht et al. (2019) applied Hashin damage criteria to predict damage evolution in composite plates under combined traction and torsion, confirming the suitability of progressive damage models for composite failure prediction [7]. Eggers et al. (2019) investigated the mechanical

response of filament-wound composite rings under tension and compression and concluded that winding angle plays a dominant role in governing stiffness and strength [8]. Özbek et al. (2019) extended this understanding by introducing intraply fibre hybridisation in filament-wound pipes, showing improved stability and energy absorption compared to single-fibre systems [9].

Advanced analytical and numerical approaches were proposed by Rafiee et al. (2019), who developed a layer-wise theoretical and numerical model to predict impact-induced damage in composite cylinders. Their results demonstrated improved accuracy compared to conventional finite element models [10]. Rafiee and Abbasi (2020) further validated progressive damage modelling through numerical and experimental analysis of hoop tensile strength in filament wound composite tubes [11]. Huang et al. (2020) developed a three-dimensional progressive damage finite element model to simulate failure in large-scale filament-wound composite pipes, achieving good agreement with experimental observations [12].

Hybrid structures combining metallic and composite components have also been explored. Zheng et al. (2020) investigated aluminium–CFRP hybrid tubes under axial crushing and showed superior energy absorption compared to monolithic aluminium or CFRP tubes [13]. Kumar et al. (2020) studied hybrid Kenaf/Glass fabric composite tubes and reported enhanced crushing stability and energy absorption due to fibre hybridisation [14]. Rafiee et al. (2020) extended theoretical modelling to composite pressure vessels subjected to combined low velocity impact and internal pressure, highlighting the complex interaction between loading modes and damage evolution[15].

More recent studies have emphasised the influence of fibre architecture, stacking sequence, and impact damage on mechanical performance. Supian et al. (2021) demonstrated that increasing winding angle significantly improves energy absorption under intermediate-velocity 14 impact loading [16]. Abd Rased and Yoon (2021) experimentally showed that asymmetrical stacking sequences strongly influence delamination behaviour in filament-wound CFRP specimens under Mode I, Mode II, and mixed-mode loading [17]. Farhood et al. (2021) reported that glass fibre hybridisation enhances low-velocity impact resistance of filament wound carbon fibre composite pipes [18]. Nikpourian et al. (2021) developed a kinetic theory based fatigue life prediction model for filament-wound CFRP composite shells, successfully capturing fatigue behaviour under cyclic loading [19].

Investigations conducted in recent years have further advanced understanding of damage progression and hybrid configurations. Chang et al. (2022) examined the quasi-static mechanical behaviour of filament-wound composite thin-walled tubes under tension, torsion, and combined loading, revealing nonlinear progressive damage behaviour[20]. Gemi et al. (2022) studied the axial compression response of impact-damaged filament-wound pipes and confirmed that prior impact significantly reduces load-carrying capacity [21]. Masoumi et al. (2022) demonstrated that hybrid-reinforced filament-wound pipes exhibit improved flexural strength and energy absorption, with numerical predictions closely matching experimental results [22]. Nagumo et al. (2022) applied continuum damage mechanics to predict transverse crack progression and failure pressure in filament-wound composite pressure vessels [23]. A comprehensive review by Azeem et al. (2022) highlighted current

challenges and future research needs in filament-wound composite pressure vessels, particularly in advanced numerical modelling [24].

The most recent studies have focused on innovative structural concepts and defect sensitivity. Xiao et al. (2023) proposed damage-resistant hybrid lay-up designs to enhance interlaminar fracture toughness [25]. Liu et al. (2023) demonstrated excellent energy absorption in hierarchical GFRP cylindrical structures under impact loading[26]. O’Neil et al. (2023) introduced a Kresling-pattern filament-wound CFRP origami tube, significantly improving energy absorption efficiency[27]. Morel et al. (2023) investigated the influence of internal defects in filament-wound SiC/SiC tubes and reported strong effects on stiffness and damage evolution [28]. Dang et al. (2024) investigated the nonlinear torsional buckling behaviour of corrugated-core sandwich toroidal shell segments coated with functionally graded graphene reinforced composite (FG-GRC) laminates under temperature variations [29]. Using the Ritz energy method, they derived explicit post-buckling torsion–deflection and torsion–twist relationships while accounting for closed boundary conditions and circumferential stress 15 effects. Their results demonstrated that both thermal loading and graphene reinforcement significantly influence torsional stiffness and post-buckling stability.

This study aims to numerically investigate the fatigue performance of hybrid CFRP shell aluminium stiffened cylindrical structures under cyclic loading. Particular emphasis is placed on evaluating the influence of aluminium helical and ring stiffeners on the structural stiffness, energy absorption capacity, and fatigue life of the composite cylindrical shell when subjected to lateral and longitudinal loading conditions. The study further examines how different stiffener configurations affect the overall fatigue behaviour and damage evolution in hybrid aluminium–CFRP cylinders.

3. Objectives

The specific objectives of the current studies are

- To study the effect of Aluminium 6061 and Ti-6Al-4V helical stiffener on stiffness and energy absorption capacity of the composite cylindrical shell under lateral and longitudinal loading
- To study the effect of Aluminium and Ti-6Al-4V helical stiffener on fatigue performance in Hybrid Aluminum-GFRP Cylinders under Cyclic Loading

4. Materials and Methodology

Figure 1. Detailed methodology for the numerical studies

Figure 1 shows the detailed methodology for conducting numerical studies on Fibre Reinforced Composite (FRC) cylindrical shell. The FE model is validated using the experimental results available in Moeinifard's work [5]. The FE model's dimensions are used as same used in the Moeinifard's work. In this study, Fatigue performance of Aluminium and Ti-6Al-4V helical stiffened FRC cylinder under cyclic loading are conducted to study the change in stress and deformation.

The material used for the stiffener of structure are taken as Aluminium 6061 and Ti6Al4V. Material properties of Aluminium 6061 and Ti6Al4V used for the current study are shown in Table 1. The material used for the shell is glass fibres with epoxy matrix and its mechanical properties are taken from Moeinifard et.al. study[30]. Mechanical properties of glass fibres and epoxy matrix are shown in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively. Orthotropic material properties of the fibre $[0]_{16}$ and $([+62/62]_4)_s$ laminate are shown in table 4. Orthotropic material properties of $([+62/62]_4)_s$ laminate is computed using classical laminate theory [1]with help of laminator software. Fiber thickness is assumed as 0.09375 mm.

Table 1. Material properties of Aluminium 6061 and Ti6Al4V

Material Properties	Aluminium 6061	Ti6Al4V
Youngs Modulus	70.29 GPa	110 GPa
Poisson Ratio	0.33	0.32
Bulk Modulus	68.91 GPa	110 GPa
Shear Modulus	26.43 GPa	42 GPa
Density	2713 Kg/m ³	4420 Kg/m ³
Yield strength	260 MPa	850 MPa
Ultimate Strength	313 MPa	950 MPa

Table 2. Average mechanical properties of Glass fibre

Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Density (Kg/m ³)	Peak Force (N)	Breakage displacement (mm)
53.6	1000	2580	42.6	4.4

Table 3. Average mechanical properties of epoxy matrix

Elastic Modulus (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Density (Kg/m ³)
1020	15.1	1100

Table 4. Orthotropic Material Properties

Orthotropic Material Properties	[0] ₁₆	([+62/-62] ₄) _s
E _x (MPa)	56000	8626
E _y (MPa)	8000	29830
E _z (MPa)	8000	8000
v _{xy}	0.22	0.25
v _{yz}	0.2	0.863
v _{xz}	0.2	0.2
G _{xy} (MPa)	4000	29600
G _{yz} (MPa)	2000	4000
G _{xz} (MPa)	4000	4000
Longitudinal Tensile Strength (MPa)	400	63
Tranverse Tensile Strength (MPa)	150	260
Longitudinal Compressive Strength (MPa)	-300	-124
Transverse Compressive Strength (MPa)	-400	-183
Shear Strength (MPa)	60	115

Damage initiation and evolution in composite structures are addressed with different damage criteria's such as maximum stress criterion, maximum strain criterion, Tsai-Wu Criterion, Puck Criterion, Hashin Damage Criterion, Damage evolution models etc. Hashin criterion is selected for the current study, which incorporates six criteria to assess the initiation of damage in tension and compression, encompassing fibre, matrix, and interfacial levels [7]. The six criteria are mentioned below:

Tensile Fiber Failure, $\sigma_{11} \geq 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_{12}^2} = \begin{cases} \geq 1, & \text{failure} \\ < 1, & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Compressive Fiber Failure, $\sigma_{11} < 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C}\right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1, & \text{failure} \\ < 1, & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Tensile matrix Failure, $\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} > 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_{23}^2} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_{12}^2} = \begin{cases} \geq 1, & \text{failure} \\ < 1, & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Compressive Matrix Failure, $\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} < 0$

$$\left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_C}\right)^2 - 1\right] + \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_{23}} + \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_{23}} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_{23}^2} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_{12}^2} = \begin{cases} \geq 1, & \text{failure} \\ < 1, & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Interlaminar Tensile Failure, $\sigma_{33} > 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_T}\right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1, & \text{failure} \\ < 1, & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Interlaminar Compressive Failure, $\sigma_{33} < 0$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_C}\right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1, & \text{failure} \\ < 1, & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

3D model of FRC cylindrical shell is modelled using Autodesk Inventor software. The dimension of the model are chosen as same as illustrated in Moeinifard's work [30], which is used for validating numerical results. The FRC cylindrical shell of dimension 160mm diameter, 360mm height are modelled. For helical stiffened shell, 3 helical stiffeners of pitch 720mm and outer diameter 157mm with square crosssection with side 6mm are modelled. The 3D FRC cylindrical shell with helical stiffeners is shown in figure 2. For numerical model Validation, Round and Flat indenters are used for studying the influence of indenter over FRC shell under transverse loading used in Moeinifard's work [30].

Figure 2 3D model of Helical Stiffened FRC cylindrical shell

Figure 0 3D model of Helical stiffened FRC shell between round and flat indenter

Figure 1 3D model of Helical stiffened FRC shell between two flat indenters

5. Numerical Model Validation

Helical stiffened FRC cylindrical shell under transverse loading between different types of indenters are developed for validating the numerical model. Different numerical model cases are need to be studied are

- Stiffened FRC cylindrical shell using helical stiffener under lateral loading between cylindrical indenter and flat platen.
- Stiffened FRC cylindrical shell using helical stiffener under lateral loading between two flat platens.

FE Mesh generated for the static structural analysis of helical stiffened cylinder loaded between cylindrical indenter and flat platen is shown in figure 3.5 (a). Similarly, for the helical stiffened cylinder loaded between two flat platens is shown in figure 3.5 (b).

Figure 5.1 Meshed FE Models

5.1 Boundary Conditions

Orthotropic properties of $([+62/62]_{4s})$ laminate is assigned to the stiffeners and fibre orthotropic properties and orientation of the cylindrical shell assigned. Orthotropic properties taken as in table 3. Rigid contact is made between indenters and shell. Damage initiation and evolution is applied using Hashin criterion. All Degree of Freedom (DOF) of bottom flat support are arrested. Lateral loading is applied on the cylinder by ramped displacement load of 120mm is applied to the indenter along y-direction over the FE Model. All other DOF of the indenter are fixed. The schematic diagram for the boundary conditions applied to the FE model is shown in figure 3.6.

Figure 5.1 Schematic diagram for applied boundary conditions

6. Structural Performance Study

The static structural analysis is conducted to evaluate the hybrid cylinder's integrity under combined axial compression load and internal pressure. For comparing the performance of Hybrid FRC cylinder with FRC stiffened cylinder (both Stiffener and shell are FRC), Three model are developed for all the cases. This specific loading configuration is designed to resemble the operational stresses encountered in aerospace vehicle structures, such as fuselage sections or propellant tanks, where internal pressurization and axial thrust forces coexist. An axial load of 10000N and cabin internal and external pressure of 0.1 MPa (atmospheric pressure) and external pressure of 0.05 MPa is considered in the FE model. In avoid the edge localised buckling, at both end of the FRC cylinder is reinforced by constraining the lateral direction. The boundary condition used for the structural analysis is shown in figure 3.7.

Figure 6 Boundary conditions used in structural analysis

6.1 Modal Analysis

Modal analysis is used to determine the dynamic characteristics of the proposed structure—specifically its natural frequencies and mode shapes. The study ensures that the operational frequency of the system remains well below the first natural frequency. This is a vital step in preventing excessive vibrations that could otherwise lead to the catastrophic delamination of the GFRP layers or the debonding of the aluminium/Ti6Al4V-composite interface. The Modal analysis is conducted followed by static structural analysis. The stress condition from the static structural analysis is used to predict the natural frequency.

6.2 Buckling Analysis

The buckling analysis is conducted to determine the critical load-carrying capacity and structural stability of the hybrid cylinder under axial compression. This study identifies the Critical Buckling Load and the associated Buckling Load Factor (BLF), which represents the ratio between the buckling load and the applied design load. Given the thin-walled nature of

the GFRP shell, this analysis is essential for predicting the transition from stable equilibrium to an unstable state, where the structure may collapse due to geometric instability rather than material failure. By evaluating various buckling modes, the research quantifies how the helical aluminium/Ti6Al4V stiffeners redistribute longitudinal stresses and increase the second moment of area of the shell wall. This step is crucial for ensuring that the stiffened configuration effectively delays the onset of localized skin wrinkling or global Euler buckling, thereby maintaining the structural integrity of the aerospace-inspired assembly. Similar to modal analysis, buckling analysis is conducted followed by static structural analysis.

6.3 Transient Structural Analysis

The transient structural analysis is conducted to evaluate the time-dependent response and long-term durability of the hybrid cylinder under dynamic conditions. This study simulates the structural behaviour of the assembly when subjected to cyclic loading, with the compressive force fluctuating between a minimum of 7500 N and a maximum of 12500 N. The load is applied at a frequency of 10 cycles per second (10 Hz) to replicate the high-frequency vibrations typically encountered in aerospace environments. By tracking the evolution of distortion and stress over specific time increments, the analysis identifies critical fatigue points where the mismatch in material properties between the aluminium/Ti6Al4V stiffeners and the GFRP shell is most pronounced. This is a vital step in predicting the total Life Cycle (N) of the component and ensuring that the interface remains intact under repeated operational stress. Boundary condition is used is similar to static structural analysis, but axial load is replace by cyclic load. The Figure 3.8 shows the cyclic load applied to FE model.

Figure 6.3 Cyclic load used in Transient Analysis

7 Results and Conclusions

The load deflection curve obtained from the simulation is shown in figure 7 and 12.28KN/mm, 14.6KN/mm and 15.13 KN/mm stiffness are obtained for GFRP Cylinder with GFRP stiffeners, Aluminium and Ti6Al4V stiffeners respectively. Maximum deformation of 0.843mm, 0.728mm, and 0.704mm are observed for GFRP Cylinder with GFRP stiffeners, Aluminium stiffeners and Ti6Al4V stiffeners respectively. Replacing the GFRP stiffeners with Aluminium and Ti6Al4V counterparts significantly enhances structural rigidity, resulting in a 13.6% and 16.4% reduction in total deformation respectively. The von Mises stress distribution plot is shown in figure 7.1, maximum equivalent stress of 63.9 MPa, 78.56 MPa and 105.76 MPa are observed for GFRP Cylinder with GFRP stiffeners, Aluminium stiffeners and Ti6Al4V stiffeners respectively. The higher stress observed in the Aluminium and Ti6Al4V-stiffened model indicates that the stiffer metallic reinforcement is successfully absorbing and carrying a larger portion of the structural load.

Figure 7 Load Deflection curve from static structural analysis

Figure 7.1 von Mises stress distribution obtained for GFRP cylinder with (a) GFRP stiffeners (b) Aluminium 6061 stiffeners and (c) Ti6Al4V stiffeners

Maximum equivalent strain of 0.0058 mm/mm, 0.0047 mm/mm and 0.0048 mm/mm are observed for GFRP Cylinder GFRP stiffeners, Aluminium stiffeners and Ti6Al4V stiffeners respectively as shown in figure 7.2. Replacing the GFRP stiffeners with Aluminium/Ti6AL4V counterparts results in a 18.9% reduction in strain, ensuring the structure remains within the acceptable limits for aerospace composite applications. In high-performance aerospace design, the allowable design strain for Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymers (GFRP) is typically limited to a range of 0.4% to 0.5% (0.004 to 0.005 mm/mm) to account for long-term environmental degradation and impact resistance (standard FAA and EASA Certification Specifications, CS-25 [31]). By reducing the strain to 0.0047 mm/mm, the hybrid configuration effectively brings the peak stress concentration closer to these established safety margins compared to the GFRP stiffened model.

Figure 7.2 Equivalent Strain distribution obtained for GFRP cylinder with (a) GFRP stiffeners (b) Aluminium 6061 stiffeners and (c) Ti6Al4V stiffeners

From the eigenvalue buckling analysis, the buckling mode plots are shown in Figures 7.3, both configurations exhibit localized shell buckling (skin wrinkling) between the helical stiffeners, characterized by periodic wave patterns on the GFRP surface. According to the Table 5, the critical buckling strength for the GFRP cylinder with GFRP stiffeners is 35.09 kN with a Buckling Load Factor (BLF) of 3.5. Also, the model with Aluminium stiffeners shows an increased buckling strength of 37.73 kN and a BLF of 3.7. For Ti6Al4V stiffeners is 39.01 kN with a Buckling Load Factor (BLF) of 3.9. Replacing the GFRP stiffeners with Aluminium stiffeners and Ti6Al4V stiffeners results in a 7.5% and 11.17% increase in the critical buckling load respectively. This improvement confirms that the higher elastic modulus of the metallic stiffeners provides superior lateral support to the shell, effectively delaying the onset of localized instability and enhancing the overall structural integrity of the hybrid assembly.

Figure 7.3 Buckling mode plots obtained for GFRP cylinder with (a) GFRP stiffeners (b) Aluminium 6061 stiffeners and (c) Ti6Al4V stiffeners

Table 5 Buckling studies results

Mode	GFRP Stiffener		Aluminium Stiffener		Ti6Al4V Stiffener	
	BLF	Buckling Strength (KN)	BLF	Buckling Strength (KN)	BLF	Buckling Strength (KN)
1	3.5094	35.094	3.7727	37.727	3.9008	39.008
2	3.5125	35.125	3.7739	37.739	3.9018	39.018
3	3.8464	38.464	4.071	40.71	4.173	41.73
4	3.8468	38.468	4.0714	40.714	4.1739	41.739
5	3.8475	38.475	4.0719	40.719	4.1755	41.755
6	3.8484	38.484	4.0722	40.722	4.1766	41.766
7	3.9819	39.819	4.109	41.09	4.1774	41.774
8	3.9869	39.869	4.1091	41.091	4.1785	41.785
9	4.0871	40.871	4.1098	41.098	4.1786	41.786
10	4.0875	40.875	4.11	41.1	4.1801	41.801

From the modal analysis, the predicted natural frequencies and its corresponding mode shapes of the both configuration of cylindrical structures. Figure 7.4 shows the first buckling mode shape of GFRP cylinder stiffened with GFRP, Aluminium and Ti6Al4V stiffeners. The mode shapes for both configurations exhibit characteristic lobar patterns along the shell circumference, indicating typical thin-walled cylindrical harmonic responses. According to Table 6, the fundamental natural frequency for the GFRP cylinder with GFRP stiffeners is 425.46 Hz and that for Aluminium and Ti6Al4V stiffeners shows a significantly higher fundamental frequency of 560.93 Hz and 571.78 Hz. Replacing the GFRP stiffeners with Aluminium and Ti6Al4V counterparts results in a 31.8% and 34.4 % increase in the first natural frequency. This upward shift in the frequency spectrum confirms that the hybrid configuration significantly enhances the stiffness-to-mass ratio of the assembly. By raising the natural frequencies, the Ti6Al4V-stiffened design effectively improves the operational safety margin, ensuring the structure remains well away from low-frequency excitation sources and potential resonance-induced failure.

Figure 7.4 Modes shapes obtained from modal analysis on (a)GFRP, (b) Aluminium and (c) Ti6Al4V stiffened Cylinder

Table 6 Natural Frequency obtained from modal analysis

Mode	Natural Frequency		
	GFRP Stiffeners	Aluminium Stiffeners	Ti6Al4V Stiffeners
1	425.46	560.93	571.78
2	430.7	607.43	616.94
3	538.8	628.58	617.42
4	539.01	628.69	650.59
5	559.06	795.44	838.12
6	559.64	795.51	838.48
7	738.41	911.89	853.06
8	739.48	921.59	942.09
9	766.86	921.61	944.79
10	768.01	951.57	967.77

7.1 Fatigue Performance Study

The transient structural analysis is conducted to evaluate the time-dependent response and long-term durability of the hybrid cylinder under dynamic conditions. This study simulates the structural behaviour of the assembly when subjected to cyclic loading, with the compressive force fluctuating between a minimum of 7500 N and a maximum of 12500 N. The load is applied at a frequency of 10 cycles per second (10 Hz) to replicate the high-frequency vibrations typically encountered in aerospace environments. By tracking the evolution of distortion and stress over specific time increments, the analysis identifies critical fatigue points where the mismatch in material properties between the aluminium/Ti6Al4V stiffeners and the GFRP shell is most pronounced. This is a vital step in predicting the total Life Cycle (N) of the component and ensuring that the interface remains intact under repeated operational stress. Boundary condition is used is similar to static structural analysis, but axial load is replace by cyclic load. The Figure 10 shows the cyclic load applied to FE model.

Figure 7.5 Cyclic load used in Transient Analysis

Figure 7.6 Equivalent alternating stress obtained for GFRP cylinder with (a) GFRP stiffeners (b) Aluminium 6061 stiffeners and (c) Ti6Al4V stiffeners from transient structural analysis

The Equivalent Alternating Stress plots in Figure 7.6 shows the maximum alternating stress for the GFRP-stiffened cylinder reached 102.86 MPa, while the Aluminium-stiffened configuration exhibited a peak of 116.27 MPa and for Ti6Al4V stiffened configuration, 160 MPa. Although the absolute stress is higher in the metallic stiffeners, this is a desirable outcome as the stiffer Aluminium 6061 and Ti6Al4V members absorbs the majority of the cyclic load, thereby shielding the GFRP shell from excessive fatigue damage.

The Aluminium-stiffened cylinder exhibits a minimum life of 1.86×10^5 cycles, whereas the GFRP-stiffened assembly shows a significantly lower minimum life of 1.16×10^5 cycles. Whereas For Ti6Al4V stiffened assembly shows a minimum life of 1.44×10^6 cycles. This represents a 11.41 times higher fatigue life for Ti6Al4V stiffened structure than that of the GFRP stiffened structure. By effectively managing the load distribution, the Ti6Al4V helical stiffeners delay the onset of structural degradation, ensuring long-term reliability under the 10 Hz aerospace-representative loading history.

Figure 12 Fatigue sensitivity Curve

The fatigue durability was evaluated by plotting the available life against a loading history scale factor, which represents a multiplier of the base cyclic load range (7500 N – 12500 N). As shown in Figure 12, the Ti6Al4V-stiffened cylinder exhibits superior fatigue resistance, maintaining a maximum life of 1×10^7 cycles up to a load factor of 0.6 and consistently outperforming the GFRP and Aluminium model at higher intensities. Conversely, the GFRP-stiffened cylinder shows immediate life degradation as the load increases, falling to approximately 1.2×10^5 cycles at the design load factor of 1.0. These results indicate that the hybrid design significantly enhances structural stability by shifting the peak stresses into the higher-fatigue-strength metallic stiffeners, effectively shielding the composite shell from early cyclic failure at 10 Hz.

7.2 CONCLUSION

The structural performance of a GFRP cylindrical shell reinforced with helical stiffeners under cyclic loading was numerically investigated to evaluate the benefits of a hybrid CFRP-Aluminium/Ti6Al4V configuration. The numerical models developed for helical-stiffened FRC cylinders under lateral loading show good agreement with experimental results, particularly in capturing the initial stiffness

for both indenter–platen and flat–platen loading conditions. This confirms the validity of the finite element modelling approach in the elastic and early nonlinear response regimes. Based on the static, modal, buckling, and transient analyses conducted on the validated numerical model, the following are the conclusions obtained from current study:

The integration of Aluminium 6061 and Ti6Al4V helical stiffeners significantly enhances the structural rigidity of the GFRP shell. Results show a 13.6% and 16.4% reduction in total deformation and an 18.9% reduction in peak equivalent strain compared to the all-composite configuration. By shifting the primary load-bearing responsibility to the stiffer metallic members, the hybrid design successfully maintains composite strain levels within the critical aerospace allowable limit of 0.0048 mm/mm.

The eigenvalue buckling analysis confirms that the hybrid configuration provides superior resistance against geometric instability. The critical buckling strength increased from 35.094 kN to 37.727 kN, a 7.5% improvement for Aluminium stiffener. For Ti6Al4V stiffeners, 11.2% improvement in critical buckling strength which is increased from 35.094 kN to 39 kN. While localized shell buckling (skin wrinkling) remains the primary failure mode for proposed designs, the Aluminium and Ti6Al4V stiffeners provide enhanced lateral support that effectively delays the onset of shell buckling.

The hybrid assembly exhibits a significantly improved dynamic response, with the fundamental natural frequency increasing by 31.8% (from 425.46 Hz to 560.93 Hz) for Aluminium stiffener and 34.4% (from 425.46Hz to 571.78 HZ) for Ti6Al4V stiffeners. This substantial shift toward a higher frequency spectrum confirms an increased stiffness-to-mass ratio, effectively isolating the structure from low-frequency operational vibrations and resonance-induced failure.

Under a 10 Hz cyclic loading history, the Ti6Al4V-stiffened cylinder demonstrates superior durability, achieving an 11.4 times higher minimum working life than GFRP stiffened configuration. The hybrid model maintained a safety factor more than 0.5 and a life of 1.44×10^6 cycles, compared to only 1.16×10^5 cycles for the GFRP-stiffened version. This proves that metallic reinforcement is essential for shielding the composite shell from early fatigue degradation.

From this thesis work, it is concluded that substituting GFRP stiffeners with Ti6Al4V significantly enhances structural performance, yielding a 16.4% increase in rigidity, a 11.2% improvement in buckling stability, and an 18.9% reduction in peak strain. Dynamically, the hybrid configuration raises the fundamental frequency by 34.4%, while transient analysis reveals a 11.4 times increase in fatigue life due to the metallic stiffeners effectively absorbing cyclic stresses. Ultimately, the hybrid design offers a robust, high-stiffness solution that ensures long-term fatigue reliability for lightweight aerospace applications.

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